

The National Education Policy, 2020: A Pathway to Reforming India's Education System

Paper Id : 19316 Submission Date : 2024-10-04 Acceptance Date : 2024-10-17 Publication Date : 2024-10-19
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13954871

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Pratiksha Bhardwaj
Assistant Professor
School Of Law
UPES
Dehradun,,Uttarakhand,
India

Abstract

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 marks a significant shift in India's approach to education, aiming to create a more holistic, flexible, and multidisciplinary system that meets the needs of 21st-century learners. This policy outlines comprehensive reforms at all levels, from early childhood education to higher education, emphasizing equitable access, critical thinking, and vocational training. With a focus on inclusivity, NEP 2020 proposes universal access to education, bridging the urban-rural educational divide, and fostering learning in regional languages. It also introduces structural changes, including the 5+3+3+4 curriculum, which is designed to align students' learning outcomes with developmental stages. The policy highlights the importance of technology integration, teacher training, and research, while promoting the autonomy of educational institutions. This paper examines the potential impact of NEP 2020 on India's educational landscape, exploring how its progressive vision can address the current challenges and build a future-ready education system.

Keywords Education Policy, Key learning, technology integration, Digital Education, Development.

Introduction

The growth of education is a continuous process, which assembles its past into present then like a living stream, flowing through the present into the future. 'The New Education Policy 2020 (hereinafter "NEP, 2020")' was approved on 29th July 2020 by the Union Cabinet chaired by the Honorable Prime Minister, giving a comprehensive structural change in higher education sector of India. This policy envisages the development of youth by imparting quality education across the country as education is the very building block of any nation. It aims to address the varying issue in higher education in India and provides comprehensive policy for higher education. The policy has incorporated both traditional and modern education structure of India to achieve the 21st century goals. The founding pillars of the policy are "access, equity, quality, affordability and accountability" for all by in education. The goals of Sustainable Development 2030 have been incorporated in the policy with an aim to make India a global superpower by making education holistic, flexible and multidisciplinary at all levels of education. It aims to harness and bring out the unique capabilities of students to align with the needs of the 21st century. It has given special emphasis on 'Socially and Economically Disadvantaged Groups (hereinafter "SEDGs")' which are based on gender, socio-cultural, geographical identities, and disabilities across the country. In higher education structural changes in regulatory bodies, rationalized institutional architecture, adoption of technology and digital education have been incorporated.

Objective of study

1. To analyze the key features of the National Education Policy (NEP), 2020.
2. To assess the impact of NEP, 2020 on the Indian education system.
3. To examine the role of NEP, 2020 in enhancing vocational and skill-based education.
4. To evaluate the role of NEP in promoting the use of technology and digital learning.
5. To investigate the impact of NEP, 2020 on the professional development of educators.
6. To explore the challenges in implementing the National Education Policy, 2020.
7. To suggest strategies for the effective implementation of NEP, 2020.

Review of Literature

The NEP 2020 represents the first major overhaul of India's education system since the National Policy on Education in 1986. It introduces a comprehensive reform covering various stages of education from early childhood to higher education. Initial reviews and analyses of the policy focus on its ambitious vision of transforming education in India to create a knowledge-based economy. Reports and official documents such as the "Draft National Education Policy 2019" and commentaries by policy experts that offer insight into the rationale behind the policy.

Several scholars have evaluated the NEP's emphasis on ECCE, recognizing it as a critical component of lifelong learning. The policy advocates for universal access to quality early childhood education and a holistic, play-based learning framework for children aged 3–6 years. Research by experts like Kaul (2020) and Sharma (2021) highlights the importance of this stage for cognitive development and explores the challenges of implementing ECCE programs in rural areas.

NEP 2020 proposes a new structure, replacing the traditional 10+2 system, focusing on foundational literacy and numeracy, and flexibility in learning. This has sparked discussions on how the new framework can enhance critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills from a young age. Studies by Singh (2021) and Aggarwal (2020) assess the 5+3+3+4 system and the policy's proposal to reduce the rigid separation between academic and vocational streams.

NEP 2020's focus on promoting multilingualism, especially using the mother tongue as a medium of instruction, has been a widely discussed aspect. Proponents argue that children learn better in their native languages, but critics raise concerns about the feasibility of implementing this policy in multilingual classrooms. Studies by Mohanty (2020) and Panda (2021) discuss the pros and cons of introducing mother-tongue education and the potential logistical challenges in diverse Indian states.

The NEP outlines a multidisciplinary approach to higher education, with flexible curriculum structures, exit options at various stages, and the introduction of a 4-year undergraduate program. Literature on these reforms explores how they aim to bridge the gap between higher education and employment. Bhattacharya (2021) and Ramesh (2020) discuss the potential benefits of the new credit-based system and its alignment with global education standards, as well as the challenges in transitioning to this structure.

A significant shift in NEP 2020 is its focus on integrating vocational education into mainstream education. Scholars have reviewed the policy's potential to bridge the skills gap and improve employment prospects, particularly in non-urban regions. Studies by Desai (2021) and Mehta (2020) emphasize the policy's approach to making vocational training accessible and explore international models of successful vocational integration.

NEP 2020 emphasizes the need for improving teacher training, setting minimum qualifications, and offering continuous professional development to educators. Literature has discussed the role of teacher quality in achieving the objectives of the policy. Research by Kumar (2020) and Pillai (2021) examines the policy's teacher education framework and the practical challenges in upgrading teacher training institutes across the country.

The policy's focus on technology-driven learning and the creation of digital infrastructure has garnered significant attention. Scholars debate the effectiveness of online education, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, and how digital divides might hinder the realization of NEP's goals. Research by Gupta (2021) and Bose (2020) focuses on the role of technology in democratizing education and the challenges posed by unequal access to digital resources in rural India.

Although the NEP 2020 is visionary, there are several hurdles in its implementation. Financial constraints, state-level resistance, and infrastructural deficits pose significant challenges. Literature has focused on policy implementation gaps and potential roadblocks. Research by Rao (2021) and Joshi (2020) discusses challenges in funding, bureaucratic hurdles, and discrepancies in the quality of education across various Indian states.

Main Text**Historical Background of Education Policy in India**

After independence the Constitution was adopted in 1950, and education became the domain of both state and central governments. The Constitution laid the principle of 'equality of educational opportunity' and 'achievement of social justice'. Education has

been put in concurrent list the state governments play a prominent role for development of primary and secondary education. Since independence India is struggling to eradicate illiteracy and poverty and various commission, committees and programs have been initiated to address this problem. The prominent were:

1. "University Education Commission (1948-1949)"
2. "Secondary Education Commission (1952-1953)"
3. "Education Commission (1964-66)" under Dr. D. S. Kothari
4. "National Policy on Education, 1968"
5. "42nd Constitutional Amendment, 1976- Education in Concurrent List"
6. "National Policy on Education (NPE), (1986)"
7. "NPE 1986 Modified in 1992" (Program of Action, 1992)
8. "T.S.R. Subramaniam Committee Report (27 May, 2016)"
9. "Dr. Kasturirangan Committee Report" (31 May, 2019) etc.

The reports of the commissions have improved the education policies from time to time and given some results. However, the success of cent percent has not been achieved in education due to various reasons be it gaps between the recommendations and implementations of these policies or administrative lapses or maybe some political and social pressures. The various drawbacks that existed in these policies have led to many lacunae in our education system. This has led to address the issue of social and economic inequalities and cultural diversity in our education system. The growth of private education system has worsened this inequality in our education system. No education policy till now has place a uniform system of education across the country or uniform quality assessment mechanism in our education system.

The timeline for New Education Policy (NEP) 2020

The education policy for the 21st century, 'National Policy of Education (NPE), 1986' is being replaced after 34 years and was initiated by 'Ministry of Human Resource Development' (hereinafter "MHRD") in January 2015 through an unprecedented collaborative, inclusive, and highly participatory consultation process. The committee under the Chairmanship of Late Shri T.S.R. Subramanian, Former Cabinet Secretary, submitted its report in May 2016 under "Committee for Evolution of the New Education Policy". After the comprehensive scrutiny of the report MHRD prepared the draft of the policy and submitted it under 'Some Inputs for the Draft National Education Policy, 2016'. Then under the Chairmanship of eminent scientist "Padma Vibhushan, Dr. K. Kasturirangan", a committee was constituted, and it submitted the Draft National Education Policy, 2019 to MHRD on 31st May 2019. For the public views/suggestions/comments the draft policy was uploaded on MHRD's website through 'My Gov Innovate' portal and stakeholders' suggestions/comments were elicited. The Union Cabinet Ministers Prakash Javadekar (I&B) and Ramesh Pokhriyal Nishank (HRD), who were instrumental in the development of the new policies, approved the New Education Policy 2020. The National Education Policy (NEP-2020), whose draft was created by a group of experts led by the former head of the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), K Kasturirangan, was evaluated by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on May 1. Goal of National Education Policy 2020 is to make "India a global knowledge superpower".

Principles of New Education Policy 2020

As envisaged by our Constitution the purpose of education is to bring engaged, productive and contributing citizens of our country to build an equitable, inclusive and plural society. This is achieved through and education system which develops human capability of having higher rational thoughts and actions, empathy and compassion towards others, courage and resilience at the time of adversity and lastly creative imagination with scientific temper based on sound ethics and values.

The fundamental principles based on which the education system and individual institutions within will be guided are as follows:

1. To guarantee the coherence and authenticity of all information, a comprehensive, interdisciplinary education encompassing the social sciences, humanities, arts, and sports is necessary for a multidisciplinary society.
2. To eliminate detrimental silos and hierarchies across various academic disciplines, curricular activities in the arts and sciences should be integrated.
3. To highlight conceptual understanding rather than learning for exams only.
4. To emphasize on power of learning and promoting multilingualism in teaching and learning.
5. To emphasize on regular formative assessment of learning instead of summative assessment.

6. To promote extensive use of technology in learning by removing obstacles in languages and providing access to Divyang students.
7. To promote rich, diverse ancient and modern culture of India based on our knowledge systems and traditions as rootedness and pride in India.
8. To ensure flexibility in the education system, a learner can select his learning interest and life path according to his talent and interests.
9. To ensure education as basic right for every child across the country.
10. To encourage genuine community and private philanthropy by making a significant investment in a robust public education system.

The Vision of New Education Policy 2020

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 envisions an education system deeply rooted in Indian culture, with the aim of positioning India as a global knowledge leader. The policy seeks to provide equitable and high-quality education to all, fostering an inclusive and dynamic society. Central to the vision is the cultivation of constitutional values, instilling in students a strong sense of duty, national pride, and global responsibility. The curriculum and pedagogy are to be designed to nurture critical knowledge, skills, and values, promoting a commitment to human rights, sustainable development, and global well-being. The NEP 2020 emphasizes creating global citizens who are also deeply connected to their Indian heritage, both in thought and action.

Key Highlights for Higher Education under New Education Policy 2020

The world is changing with rapid pace and knowledge plays a pivotal role in scientific and technological advancements. The skilled workforce with multidisciplinary abilities across science social science and humanities will be required in the future to make India a super power. The education policy has laid down the emphasis on creative potential of the individual by imbibing the Indian culture of 'knowledge (Jnan), wisdom (Pragyaa) and truth (Satya)'. The purpose of higher education is not only to educate individuals for the preparation of life but to complete the realization and liberation of self. To be a global leader in education more and younger Indians are required to opt for higher education and contribute towards sustainable livelihood and development. The key highlights for higher education are as follows:

Increase Gross Enrolment Ratio to 50 % by 2035

'The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 sets an ambitious target of increasing the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in higher education, including vocational education, from 26.3% in 2018 to 50% by 2035.' To achieve this, the policy envisions adding 35 million new seats to higher education institutions. A key strategy to meet this objective is the expansion and development of higher education institutions, with a particular emphasis on strengthening public institutions to ensure equitable access to quality education across the country.

Comprehensive Multidisciplinary Training

Undergraduate education under the policy will be comprehensive, multidisciplinary, and broad-based. It will feature flexible curricula, innovative topic combinations, integrated vocational education, and numerous entry and exit points with relevant certification. A three- or four-year undergraduate program with several exit options and the necessary certifications can be completed within this time frame. For instance, an Advanced Diploma follows the first year, a bachelor's degree follows the third year, and a bachelor's with Research follows the fourth year. To facilitate the transfer and computation of academic credits toward a final degree, an Academic Bank of Credit will be created and digitally stored for academic credits obtained from various Higher Education Institutions (HEI). The creation of Multidisciplinary Education and Research Universities (MERUS) to rival IITs and IIMs and serve as national models for the greatest multidisciplinary education that meets international standards. As the premier organization for developing a robust research culture and expanding research capabilities throughout higher education, the National Research Foundation (NRF) will be established.

Regulatory Bodies for Higher Education

The Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) is set to serve as a unified regulatory body for all higher education, excluding medical and legal fields. Under its umbrella, four autonomous entities will operate: the Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) for funding, the General Education Council (GEC) for standard-setting, the National

Accreditation Council (NAC) for accreditation, and the National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NERC) for regulation. The HECI will employ faceless technological interventions to enforce compliance and penalize institutions that fail to meet established standards. Both public and private universities will be subject to the same academic, accreditation, and regulatory guidelines, ensuring uniformity across the higher education landscape.

Rationalized Institutional Architecture

Large, lively, multidisciplinary universities with ample resources that offer top-notch instruction, research, and community involvement will replace higher education establishments. A wide range of establishments will be permitted by the concept of university, including autonomous degree-granting colleges, research-intensive universities, and teaching-intensive universities. College affiliation will be phased out over the course of 15 years, and a step-by-step process for giving institutions varying degrees of autonomy will be developed. It is intended that each college will eventually grow into a constituent college of a university or an autonomous institution that grants degrees.

Motivated, Energized, and Capable Faculty

The New Education Policy 2020 offers suggestions for inspiring, invigorating, and enhancing faculty capacity through autonomous, transparent hiring procedures that are well-defined, autonomy in curriculum development and pedagogy, rewards for performance, and advancement into institutional leadership. Faculty who fails to uphold fundamental standards will be held responsible.

Teacher Education at Higher Education

The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) will collaborate with the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) to develop a comprehensive National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE) 2021. By 2030, the minimum qualification for teachers will be a four-year integrated B.Ed. degree. Strict measures will be implemented to address the issue of low-quality independent Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs), ensuring higher standards in teacher training programs across the country.

Mentoring Mission for Students at Higher Education

A National Mission for Mentoring will be established, drawing on a vast pool of distinguished senior and retired faculty members, including those proficient in Indian languages. These experienced educators will provide both short-term and long-term mentoring, as well as professional support, to university and college teachers. This initiative aims to enhance the quality of teaching by fostering continuous professional development through guidance from seasoned faculty.

Financial support for students

There will be an effort to reward the merit of pupils who fall under the SC, ST, OBC, and other SEDG categories. The purpose of the extended National Scholarship Portal is to monitor, assist, and track the academic achievement of students who are awarded scholarships. It will be encouraged for private higher education institutions to provide more scholarships and free ships to their students.

Open and Distance Learning

This will be made larger to contribute significantly to raising the Gross Enrollment Ratio. There will be steps made to make sure it is on par with the best in-class programs, including credit-based recognition of MOOCs, support for research, enhanced student services, and online courses and digital repositories.

Online Education and Digital Education

In response to the recent increase in pandemics and epidemics, comprehensive recommendations have been made to promote online education, ensuring the availability of high-quality, alternative learning options when traditional, in-person instruction is not possible. To support this initiative, the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) will establish a dedicated unit responsible for the development of digital content,

infrastructure, and capacity building, addressing the needs of both higher education and K-12 e-learning systems. This will ensure resilience and adaptability in the education sector.

Technology in education

The National Educational Technology Forum (NETF), an independent organization, will be established to offer a forum for the open discussion of technology-assisted planning, administration, assessment, and learning. All educational levels will benefit from the appropriate integration of technology in order to facilitate teacher professional development, optimize classroom procedures, increase educational access for underprivileged populations, and simplify the planning, administration, and management of education.

Promotion of Indian languages

The New Education Policy emphasizes the importance of strengthening language departments in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), particularly Sanskrit, while also establishing key institutions such as the Indian Institute of Translation and Interpretation (IITI) and the National Institutes for Pali, Persian, and Prakrit. It advocates for expanding the use of mother tongue and local languages as mediums of instruction in more HEI programs to preserve and promote the vibrancy of all Indian languages. Additionally, internationalization of education will be supported through institutional collaboration, increased faculty and student mobility, and encouraging renowned global universities to establish campuses in India.

Professional Education

The higher education system will include all professional education as a fundamental component. The goal of independent technical universities, universities of health sciences, law schools, and agricultural colleges, among others, is to develop into multidisciplinary establishments.

Challenges Ahead for New Education Policy

The much-awaited New Education Policy 2020 is being implemented after three decades and education sector welcomed it as new path is paved for education system in India. By allowing global institutions to set up campuses in India, it will open education system in maintaining high talent in India as students can pursue education in our country. However the various challenges which can be faced are as follows:

Online Education and Digital Education: Although we have entered into digital era, in India poor internet connectivity especially in rural areas and lack of healthy infrastructure would be a challenge to resolve in New Education Policy. There is lack of upgraded digital equipments and trained teachers who can teach online especially in rural India.

Centralization of Higher Education: The New Education Policy 2020 is going to replace the existing regulatory bodies' viz. UGC, AICTE etc with a single educational regulatory body at central level. Further, a Higher Education Commission of India is being setup for entire higher education excluding medical and legal education. The biggest challenge is monopoly and control at central level and increasing role of private players in education.

Privatization of Higher Education: As global institutions are interested in setting up campuses in India it is going to create an unhealthy competition among the existing Indian institutions. The thrust in education policy on measures to compete with foreign institutions is missing. The infrastructure support to the educational institutions and orientation of the entities involved in education system is going to be a challenge in the near future. Also, with global players coming in India the cost of education will increase and will be a challenge in country like India.

Implementation of 6% of GDP in education: The New Education Policy aims to increase investment in education to 6% of GDP which is the challenging part in its implementation in the coming future. As it was aimed by the education policy of 1984 to invest 6% of GDP and at present it stands to close to 3% of GDP. The implementation of this objective has not been achieved by previous governments.

Conclusion

Education is the key to the development of society, peace to the world, greater insights to mankind. To make India "Vishav Guru" the robust education policy is the need of the hour

and its implementation and impact on students will be its report card. 'The National Education Policy' is progressive shift towards scientific approach in education by reaching to all students at different levels in both rural and urban India. It will lead to overall increase in literacy level and emerge India as global knowledge superpower. In higher education the option to exit from the multidisciplinary courses will boost vocational qualifications and impart practical knowledge which is required in today's competitive world. The rationalization of regulatory bodies and centralized control will remove the various bottlenecks in the implementation of the New Education Policy. The impetus on online education will change the image of India worldwide as a global power in science and technology. However, in the past too many education policies had come but could not yield the desired results due to political and social issues. It is to be seen how this regime will implement this New Education Policy in pith and substance to yield the desired results.

References

1. *Government of India. (2020). National Education Policy 2020. Ministry of Education.*
2. *Jha, P., & Parvati, P. (2021). Understanding the National Education Policy 2020. Economic and Political Weekly, 56(4), 34-41.*
3. *Sharma, K. (2021). NEP 2020: Transforming India's Education System. Journal of Indian Education, 47(1), 12-28.*
4. *Kumar, R. (2021). Challenges and Opportunities in Implementing NEP 2020. Indian Journal of Educational Research, 39(2), 45-59.*
5. *NITI Aayog. (2021). Education Reforms in India: A Roadmap for the Future. New Delhi: NITI Aayog.*
6. *Suresh, N. (2019). Towards 'schoolification' of early childhood years: Draft national education policy 2019. Economic and Political Weekly, 54(40), 17-20.*
7. *Sharma, G., Mittal, R., & Zayan. (2023). Teacher Education in India's National Education Policy 2020: Knowledge Traditions, Global Discourses and National Regulations. Contemporary Education Dialogue, 20(2), 256-282.*
8. *Sharma, G., & Singh, S. (2023). Locating Children's Right to Education in India's National Education Policy 2020. Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies (JCEPS), 21(2).*
9. *Sengupta, P. (2021). NEP 2020 and the language-in-education policy in India—a critical assessment. Economic and Political Weekly, 56(43), 45-52.*
10. *Pal, Y. (2005). National curriculum framework. New Delhi, India: NCERT. Retrieved March, 7, 2014.*